

Automated LIBS-based classification for spent refractories from the steel industry for high-value recycling

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Abstract

Refractory products are a vital element in all high-temperature processes, especially in the steel production. The re-use of refractory material has a high potential to reduce waste production and primary raw material consumption. To allow high-grade recycling and re-use of refractories, efficient separation of the different types of refractory materials based on their chemical composition, combined with an efficient removal of impurities, is essential. The different types are mainly composed of the elements magnesium, aluminium, silicon, calcium and carbon, as well as other materials to improve the properties such as chromium.

To determine the ability of LIBS to classify different refractory materials, test measurements were performed on the LIBS-based sorting system iSort at the Fraunhofer ILT. With the data

from the 3D detection the best spot for the LIBS-measurement is calculated and sent to the LIBS-system. Furthermore the system comprises a novel feature to combine information of the 3D-detection system with the information of the LIBS measurement to enhance the sorting abilities. The system can easily be adapted to the material to be sorted, thus it is possible to measure small cuttings up to big bricks. A versatile multi-CCD spectrometer makes it possible to measure whole spectra from the laser-induced plasma as well as several individual emission lines at a high measurement frequency. This allows the measurement of various materials such as metals, electronic scrap or ceramics like refractories.

In order to determine the elemental composition of the different refractory bricks a combination of different LIBS approaches is used. For each measurement a tailored laser pulse train is irradiated on the sample for surface preparation, enabling the penetration of not representative dust layers. As the composition of used bricks can deviate locally, several selected surface locations are evaluated within less than a second to obtain a high representativeness of the classification.

Several spectral lines of each element, which is required for the distinction of the different types of refractories, are recorded simultaneously and evaluated. It is demonstrated in lab scale tests that the three main classes of refractory material can be efficiently distinguished. Upscaling for industrial tests and approaches to separate up to 8 subclasses will be presented.

Introduction

Background and aim

Raw materials are of primary importance for the refractory industry with availability of quality materials and security of supply as main topics. Indeed they account for about 40 to 50% of the refractory costs and have the major influence on the quality of the finished products. Closing the material loop of refractories, the use of spent refractories for the production of new refractory products will reduce the total cost of raw materials and will make the production of refractories in Europe more competitive. For society as a whole, shortage of primary raw materials and environmental concerns drive the need for sustainable waste treatment and working towards closing material cycles.

From the available refractory materials at least eight different refractory products are usually recycled in remarkable quantities which can be grouped into magnesia-based, doloma-based and alumina-based fractions (Table 1).

Group	Type	Composition
MgO-based	Fired MgO (FM)	High MgO, no C, low CaO
	MgO-C with antioxidant (MCA)	High MgO, 5 – 15 wt-% C, low CaO, antioxidant (Al)
	MgO-C without antioxidant (MC)	High MgO, 5 – 15 wt-% C, low CaO
Doloma-based	Fired doloma (FD)	High MgO, high CaO, no C
	Doloma carbon (DC)	High MgO, high CaO, 5-15 wt-% C
Alumina-based	Fired bauxite (FB)	High Al, Al/Si ~8/1, low CaO/MgO
	Fired andalusite (FA)	High Al, Al/Si ~2/1, low CaO/MgO
	Fired chamotte (FC)	High Al, Al/Si ~1/1, low CaO/MgO

Table 1: Properties of the 8 refractory types studied and their characteristic composition features

The main challenge in the recycling process is the proper separation of the initial “waste” material ensuring its re-usage in significant quantities. The purity of spent refractories is of vital importance in re-using them in high quality refractories. The presence of unwanted impurities in the recycled refractory materials would decrease the durability of the new finished products or would limit the amount of recycled material that can be admixed to the primary raw material. A key technology to enable automated separation is the identification of individual pieces of spent refractories. Direct laser analysis offers the capabilities to fulfil the sensor requirements for industrial operation in a separation plant.

Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) sensor

Laser light is predestined for the online measurement of physical and chemical variables, like, for example, the geometry of objects or their material composition. Laser measurement methods work fast and over distances of several centimetres to metres. For fast multi-element analysis of many materials, laser direct analysis based on emission spectrometry of laser-induced plasmas is suitable. Since also light elements, like Mg, can be measured, the LIBS analysis is ideal for the sorting of refractories.

If the beam of a pulsed laser is focused on a measured object, power densities in the range of GW/cm² are reached locally for short time. These are sufficient to vaporize every material, to dissolve the chemical bonds and heat the material to temperatures above 10 000 °C. In this state, the material emits light in its specific spectral lines, which is detected with a

spectrometer within a few microseconds. The spectrally resolved detection of the emitted line radiation allows the qualitative and quantitative determination of the composition of the object. The purely optical excitation and simultaneous measurement of the spectral lines enable an evaluation of metallic and non-conductive material within just a few milliseconds. It also enables the analysis of fast-moving objects.

The LIBS method was already introduced to different industrial applications, especially for process control [Noll 2012]. The method has also proven effective for fully automatic measurement. It has, for example, already been used for the analysis of metallic raw materials for material recycling [Werheit et al 2011] and thanks to further development is also available for use in mineral processing.

Preliminary test measurements on iSort

To determine the ability of LIBS to classify different refractory materials, test measurements were performed on the LIBS-based sorting system iSort at the Fraunhofer ILT (Figure 1). This sorting system was designed to carry out measurements and sorting trials of different materials, such as metals, e-scrap or minerals, in a flexible arrangement. Thus, we are able to show the advantages of the LIBS-based sorting on a wide range of materials.

Figure 1: LIBS-based sorting system iSort

The principle set-up of the 3D scanning LIBS technique was described before and will not be introduced here in detail [Aydin et al 2004]. The method is based on a combined 3D single particle detection system and a LIBS analyser guided by a 3D galvo-scanner system, both installed above a conveyor belt. Figure 2 shows the principle set-up of the LIBS sorter in a schematic drawing.

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the iSort sorting system. Objects are moving from left to right on a conveyor belt at velocities of up to 5 m/s (1). A 3D camera measures the position and shape of the particles (2). A pulsed laser beam irradiates the pieces within a measuring volume of $600 \times 600 \times 250 \text{ mm}^3$ (3). The laser-induced plasma light emerging from the piece is spectroscopically evaluated and a sorting decision is taken within a few milliseconds. The samples are separated in different bins according to their elemental composition using pneumatic blow bars (4) at the end of the conveyor belt.

The measuring volume amounts to $600 \times 600 \times 250 \text{ mm}^3$ located above the conveyor belt. The galvo-scanner mirrors are capable to deflect the laser beam within a few milliseconds on moving samples at velocities up to 5 m/s at a distance of about 900 mm. Figure 3 shows the identification of a refractory brick scanned by the 3D detection system. The points of the grid mark the measurement points where the 3D object recognition analyzed the surface with respect to the suitability for the subsequent LIBS measurement. Several of these

dots are chosen as the most suitable surface points.

Figure 3: One spent refractory brick scanned by 3D-detection system. Left: Heightmap of a spent refractory brick; Right: Brick with evaluated grid-points.

The combined targeting precision of 3D detection and LIBS-scanner system is ± 1.5 mm. In contrast to conventional LIBS techniques where the laser beam is at a fixed position, both the specimen under investigation and the laser beam are in motion.

For preliminary tests LIBS measurements are carried out at different pre-defined locations on fresh refractory reference samples by adjusting the laser beam direction. The data is evaluated separately to detect the inherent inhomogeneity of the material. In contrast to this valuable information, the surface of the used bricks is usually contaminated with dust and other adhesions which are not relevant for the recycling process and thus not for the classification. To avoid disturbances of the material identification by such contaminations, the laser burst consists of two components which are separated in time, one for cleaning and the other for the analytical measurement, but co-located on the moving object. Thereby, a contamination layer with a thickness in the order of 100 μ m can be penetrated. Since the location of examination can be freely chosen for each measurement, analytical information can be derived even from deeper regions of the material by repeated application on one spot.

The data evaluation takes into account the emissions from the major matrix elements Ca, Mg, Si, and Al, as well as from minor elements of interest such as C, Cr and Ti. Using a pre-defined classification scheme, each piece of refractory is assigned to a sorting fraction (shown in table 1) in such a way as to keep the output within the adjustable recycling specifications. To establish the classification scheme, LIBS measurements were carried out on a set of freshly

produced refractory materials of known composition. Fig. 4 presents the laser-induced plasma on pieces of fresh refractory samples during the LIBS analysis.

Figure 4: Laser-induced plasma on pieces of fresh refractory.

Table 2 shows the capability of the laser direct analysis to distinguish the 8 examined kinds of fresh refractories by 5 LIBS measurements per sample. To determine the values of the table, different elemental, spectral lines of refractory samples were measured and the mean and standard deviation of each class was calculated. With these values, the probabilities were calculated with which a sample of a class is correctly assigned [Werheit, 2011]. It can be seen that the distinction between the three main groups can be carried out with an accuracy of over 99%. A distinction within the main groups leads in over 90% of cases to a correct result.

C_i	MC	MCA	FM	FD	DC	FB	FA	FC
MC		98.1	96.0	99.9	99.8	99.9	99.9	99.9
MCA	98.1		98.1	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
FM	96.0	98.1		99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
FD	99.9	99.9	99.9		94.3	99.9	99.9	99.9
DC	99.8	99.9	99.9	94.3		99.9	99.9	99.9
FB	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9		99.0	93.5
FA	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.0		92.3
FC	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9	93.5	92.3	

Table 2: Calculated identification correctnesses for eight refractory classes.

Outlook

The re-use of spent refractories will become mandatory in the future in the refractory industry due to environmental and commercial reasons.

Currently the components of the 3D scanning LIBS measurements are installed into a system that is able to perform the mechanical sorting of the spent refractory bricks. Further work is ongoing to be able to identify the eight different families of refractories thanks to the LIBS system. Regarding the mechanical handling, the next step for the demonstration equipment is to prove reliability under industrial conditions which will be done onsite at the facility of Recmix in Genk, Belgium.

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